

Context

The objective of GIFFT is to develop a sustainable, hybrid, and biofuel flexible heat production technology and process that can be integrated into industrial glass manufacturing through efficient use of plasma-assisted combustion and gasification systems.

Challenges

The glass industry is at a critical juncture when facing the pressing need for an energy transition and increased circularity to align with the European Green Deal's objectives. The GIFFT project emerges as a beacon of innovation and sustainability in this scenario. It proposes a novel, sustainable hybrid and fuel-flexible technology aimed at revolutionising the glass industry. This cutting-edge approach is expected to achieve a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions per tonne of glass produced.

Ambition

The concept of GIFFT is to develop and validate a flexible hybrid furnace operation for optimal use of freely available low-cost green electricity and low-carbon biofuels to facilitate the transition from natural gas towards a new low-carbon and more dynamic heat production. The GIFFT process can propose high fuel flexibility and more dynamic operation regarding energy and fuel market changes by combining plasma-assisted biomass gasification and plasma-assisted combustion. The process is designed to enable continuous operation of the glass-making plant units throughout the year with many operating hours. The hybrid operational and fuel flexibility is analysed using standard flow sheets to calculate energy and mass balances by changing between four main modes: Base Case, Biomass Case, Green Electricity Case, and Green Hydrogen Case. While the key enabling technologies are tested and validated to reach TRL-5 at the end of the project.

Approach

The first combustion tests were carried out to visually assess the flame geometry for adaptation to existing incinerators. This test compared the flames of different fuel-oxygen compositions produced by conventional and plasma-assisted combustors. In the case of conventional combustion, the flame was generated using non-premixed combustion of natural gas (CH₄ ~96vol.%) and oxygen or hydrogen and oxygen. The thermal capacity of the burner was about 80 kW. In the case of the plasma-assisted burner prototype, the flame was generated from the same mixtures while maintaining a thermal capacity of up to 50% of the total energy released as electricity.

Results

H₂:O₂ | 26:13 Nm³/h | Q_f - 80 kW_{th}
visual flame length 0.9 m

CH₄:O₂ | 8:16 Nm³/h | 80 kW_{th}
visual flame length 1.0 m

H₂:O₂ | 15:7.5 Nm³/h | P_{el} - 42 kW | Q_f - 45 kW_{th}
visual flame length 0.6 m

CH₄:O₂ | 4.5:9 Nm³/h | P_{el} - 42 kW | Q_f - 45 kW_{th}
visual flame length 0.6 m

Figure. Photos of visual flame length assessment tests using two combustion systems: standard oxy-burner for glass melting furnace (upper images) and plasma-assisted oxy-burner (lower images).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Initial investigations have allowed us to identify the optimum gas feed points for the prototype burner to achieve flexibility and a wide range of operating parameters. In the next stages, the plasma-assisted burner will be further developed to assess not only the geometrical characteristics of the flame but also other key parameters such as flame spectral emissions, heat radiation intensity, pollutant emissions, etc.

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